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Measuring bismuth content of thin GaAsBi layers in cross-sectional STEM-EDXS

The bismuth (Bi) content in gallium arsenide bismuth ($\text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Bi}_x$) determines the emission of this narrow bandgap semiconductor alloy and therefore needs to be measured with high precision. We have studied a sample with two quantum wells (Fig. 1), the wider of which was also investigated by STEM-EDXS at 200kV (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1: ADF STEM of STB29 at 1MX [1]

Fig. 2: Energy-dispersive X-ray spectrum (EDXS) from the centre of 17nm thick layer of GaAsBi in sample STB29. Sample thickness is around 80nm [2].

Quantification of the Bi and Ga X-ray lines yields apparent Bi concentrations on the group V sub-lattice that depend strongly on the lines used, from $7.7 \pm 0.7\%$ for Bi_M/Ga_K , over $10.7 \pm 1.8\%$ for Bi_L/Ga_L (most reliable) to $14.6 \pm 1.7\%$ for Bi_M/Ga_L . This large a spread is unacceptable for a useful quantification. The errors quoted are the statistical errors from Oxford Instruments ISIS 300 with absorption correction. We will use simulations of X-ray generation and absorption to calculate self-consistent k^* -factors [3] based on the K/L ratios measured for Ga (or As) X-ray lines as an estimate for an improved, self-consistent internal absorption correction.

References:

- [1] T. Walther, R.D. Richards, F. Bastiman. *Cryst. Res. Technol.* **50**:1 (2015) 38-42
- [2] F. Bastiman, Y. Qiu, T. Walther. *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* **326** (2011) 012060
- [3] T. Walther, X. Wang. Proc. EMAG 2015. *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* **644** (2015) 012006